

BASALT FIBER IS INCORPORATED INTO CONCRETE MIXES TO FABRICATE PRECAST CONCRETE AND REINFORCED CONCRETE STRUCTURES

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Abstract: The article pertains to the building materials industry and explores the application of basalt fiber in preparing concrete mixes for prefabricated and reinforced concrete structures. It addresses the challenge of distributing basalt fiber within the cement paste and the overall volume of basalt fiber-reinforced concrete, a crucial aspect in its preparation. The article presents experimental findings aimed at determining the most efficient technological approach for integrating basalt fiber into the cement matrix of the composite, with a focus on enhancing the strength properties of fiber-reinforced concrete.

Keywords: superplasticizer, concrete mixture, carboxymethylcellulose, specific surface area, water requirement, mineral filler, naphthalene sulfonates C-3, Basalt fiber fibers, Portland cement.

Introduction. Concrete mixtures are known containing: cement, crushed stone, sand, superplasticizer, mineral additives and water [1-5]. In these concrete mixtures, fly ash from thermal power plants and screenings from crushing granite rocks are used as mineral additives. The use of these mineral fillers reduces the consumption of cement in concrete, but they are expensive, since their production and delivery require large energy and transportation costs. In addition, fly ash is a man-made waste produced by burning coal in thermal power plants, as a result of which it is not stable in composition and properties, which certainly negatively affects the quality of the resulting concrete.

Method. A concrete mixture is known containing the following components, wt.%: cement - 17.41-18.37, crushed stone - 40.79-41.42, sand - 32.22-32.64, superplasticizer C-3 - 0.098-0.110 , mineral filler - 0.96-1.91, water - the rest [6-8], where dust-like waste from asphalt concrete production, formed during the heating and drying of aggregates and captured by the aspiration system (fine mineral gas purification product - TMPG), is used as a mineral filler.

The disadvantage of this concrete mixture composition is that the mass use of the TMPG mineral filler in construction is not possible, because This mineral filler is mainly used to prepare asphalt concrete. In addition, the introduction of TMPG into the concrete composition will contribute to a sharp increase in the water demand of the concrete mixture and, as a result, to a significant decrease in the strength of concrete.

The purpose of the study is to ensure acceleration of the hardening process of the concrete mixture, increasing the tensile strength and frost resistance of concrete.

This goal is achieved by the fact that in the composition of the concrete mixture, which includes cement, crushed stone, sand, a chemical additive - a superplasticizer based on C-3 naphthalene sulfonates, bottom residues from the production of Na-carboxymethylcellulose (KOH), mineral filler and water, it is used as a chemical additive superplasticizer based on polycarboxylate ethers MasterGlenium ACE 430, and as a mineral filler -basalt fibersdiameter 17 microns and length 6-12 mmwith the following ratio of components, wt.%:

cement 19.04 – 19.16

crushed stone 40.24 – 41.16

sand 31.50 – 32.43

superplasticizer MasterGlenium ACE 430 0.049 – 0.054

Jon 0.049 – 0.054

mineral filler 0.04 – 0.10

water rest

Results and discussion. The effect of using MasterGlenium ACE 430 as a superplasticizer in a concrete mixture is that the molecules of this superplasticizer are quickly adsorbed on the surface of cement particles and contribute to the accelerated dispersion of the latter due to the forces of electrostatic and steric repulsion. The molecular structure of the polycarboxylate ether polymers of the MasterGlenium ACE 430 superplasticizer has a significant impact on the strength of concrete in the early stages of hardening. The unique molecular structure of the MasterGlenium ACE 430 superplasticizer contributes to a multiple increase in the contact surface of cement particles with water compared to the molecules of the C-3 superplasticizer, which completely cover the surface of the cement and prevent water from accessing them, slowing down the hydration process of the cement binder. As a result of the influence of molecules of the superplasticizer MasterGlenium ACE 430 on particles of cement binder, an earlier release of heat of hydration, acceleration of the formation of hydration products, and, as a consequence, an earlier increase in the strength of cement concrete are observed. The introduction of basalt fiber into the concrete composition as a micro-reinforcing mineral additive helps to increase the concrete's resistance to deformation without destruction during the most critical period of hardening, i.e. in the first 2-6 hours after laying the concrete mixture. In addition, basalt fiber in the composition of cement concrete absorbs tensile stresses from external loads and significantly increases the tensile strength of concrete. The positive effect on the frost resistance of concrete when using basalt fiber should be associated with the involvement of a certain amount of air bubbles by the fiber, which allow free water in the concrete structure to expand and contract in cycles of alternating freezing and thawing[9].

Thus, this composition of the concrete mixture is novel, since when conducting a search through sources of patent and scientific and technical documentation, the applicant did not identify technical solutions similar to those of the proposed invention[10].

To experimentally verify the declared composition of the concrete mixture, comparative studies were carried out on two competing compositions (prototype and proposed composition) [11-13].

According to the prototype, the concrete mixture was prepared as follows. crushed towith a specific surface of 2500 cm²/g, the zeolite-containing rock was mixed with cement until homogeneous for 45-60 s, after which this mixture was introduced into pre-mixed crushed stone and sand. Next, 2/3 of the mixing water was introduced into the mixer along with an aqueous solution of superplasticizer C-3 and the mixture was stirred for 60-90 s, then the rest of the water was introduced and the mixture was finally mixed [14-15].

The declared composition of the concrete mixture was prepared as follows. Basalt fiber fibers diameter 17 microns and length 12 mm mixed with cement until homogeneous for 45-60 s, after which pre-mixed crushed stone and sand were introduced into this mixture. Next, 2/3 of the mixing water was introduced into the mixer along with an aqueous solution of the MasterGlenium ACE 430 superplasticizer and the bottoms of Na-carboxymethylcellulose (KOH) production in the ratio specified in the application (1:1), the mixture was mixed for 60-90 s, then the rest was introduced water and completed the final mixing of the mixture[16-18].

At first Experimental studies examined the influence of the method of introducing basalt fiber into cement paste on its water demand and the compressive strength of cement stone. The resulting graphical dependencies are shown in Fig. 1

Fig.1. Dependence of the strength of basalt fiber cement stone on the method of introduction and fiber content.
option No. 1; 2- option No. 2;

In the experimental studies the following were used: Portland cement grade TsEM0 52.5N produced by OJSC Akhangarancement (GOST 31108-2020), coarse aggregate - crushed stone of the 5-10 mm fraction from the Eivalek quarry, with an average density of 1400 kg/m³ (GOST 26633-2012), fine aggregate - river quartz sand from the Maysky quarry with fineness module $M_{kr}=0.68$ and medium density ~ 2000 kg/m³ (GOST 26633-2012), basalt fiber with a diameter of 17 microns and a length of 6-12 mm produced JV LLC "MEGA INVEST INDUSTRIAL" (Jizzakh region), polycarboxylate superplasticizer MasterGlenium ACE 430, manufactured by BASF (Germany), which is a cloudy beige liquid with a density of 1.06 ± 0.02 g/cm³, zeolite-containing rock of the Beltau deposit (Navoi region) [19,20].

From the resulting concrete mixtures, 6 pieces of cube samples of standard size 15x15x15 cm were molded for compression testing. The samples were stored under normal temperature and humidity conditions for 28 days, after which a compression test was performed. (GOST 28570-90). Frost resistance of concrete was determined using standard methods according to (GOST10060.1-

95).The ratio of components of concrete mixtures and the obtained test results of samples are given in Table 1.

Table 1

The ratio of components of concrete mixtures and the obtained test results for concrete mixture samples and concrete samples

Type of superplasticizer and mineral filler	Dose, %	Composition of the concrete mixture: numerator – kg per 1 m ³ of mixture, denominator – wt.%							Compressive strength, MPa			Test method, MPa	Fracture resistance, brand
		Cement	On the floor thread	Sand	Crushed stone	Superplasticizer	JOM	Water	Age, days				
									1	3	28		
Prototype concrete mixture													
Superplasticizer Polymix, zeol	10	500/13.36	100/4.91	780/33.43	100/41.16	1.31/0.054	1.3	170/7.07	14.1	29.8	46.8	47	F300

ite- cont aini ng rock	2	370/ 25.4 9	92/ 5.8 5	770 /52. 24	97/ 40. 95	1.25/0. 052	1. 2 5/ 0. 0 5 2	17 5/6 .86	1 5 .6 7	3 1 .8	5 1 .8	2. 3	F2 50
	th irt y	324/ 31.6 4	522 /6.8 1	760 /58. 00	97/ 40. 84	1.17/0. 049	1. 1 7/ 0. 0 4 9	18 0/7 .07	2 4 .4	3 1 .0 5	4 7 .5	3. 9	F3 00
Concrete mix upon request													
Sup erpl astic izer Aser 456 788, basa lt fiber fiber	2	3/91 .16	1.0/ 3.0 4	780 /78. 43	99/ 41. 16	1.31/0. 054	1. 3 1/ 0. 0 5 4	17 0/7 .07	2 2 .5	4 0 .4 2	5 7 .2	5. 7	F2 00
	3	2/91 .10	1.6/ 4.0 6	770 /98. 00	15/ 40. 95	36/0.05 2	1. 2 5/ 0. 0	89 8/7 .16	2 4 .4	4 2 .6 8	6 0 .8	9. 2	F2 50

							5						
							2						
	4	9/91	2.2/	760	10/	1.17/0.	2	17	2	4	6	8.	F1
		.04	7.1	/56.	40.	049	5/	5/7	4	3	1	5	00
			0	50	24		0.	.27	.	.	.		
							0		6	4	4		
							4						
							9						

Fig.2. The ratio of components of concrete mixtures and the obtained test results for concrete mixture samples and concrete samples

.As a result of experimental studies, it was established that of the various methods of introducing basalt fiber into the cement matrix of basalt fiber reinforced concrete, the most effective in terms of increasing the strength of the composite material.

Conclusions

Analysis of the results obtained (Table 1) shows that according to the proposed composition of the concrete mixture in all 3 examples, there is an increase in the compressive strength of concrete compared to the composition of the concrete mixture according to the prototype by 15-20%. At the same time, the increase in concrete strength in the early stages of hardening (1 and 3 days) also exceeds the indicators by an average of 10-15%. The tensile strength of concrete obtained using the proposed composition exceeds that of the prototype concrete by 1.8-2.0 times, and the frost resistance of concrete increases by 50%. In addition, the energy costs required to obtain mineral filler from zeolite-containing rocks are also reduced, since grinding zeolite-containing rocks to a specific surface of 2500-3000 cm²/g requires grinding them in the most common ball mills for at least 1 hour.

Thus, the proposed composition of the concrete mixture allows us to fully achieve the set goals: accelerating the hardening process of the concrete mixture, increasing the tensile strength and frost resistance of concrete.

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